

CANDLE

International Partner Projects

**REDUCE THE
BURDEN OF
CANCER IN
EUROPE**

More Information

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Glossary

National Cancer Data Nodes (NCDN) are federated hubs for standardising and harmonising cancer data procedures within their country. CANDLE will support the development of NCDN by

European Health Data Space (EHDS)

An EU framework (Regulation 2025/327) that enables secure sharing of health data for healthcare (primary use) and for research, policy, and regulation (secondary use), while ensuring strong privacy and patient control.

European Cancer Information Portal (EU-CIP) is developing a digital portal with patient-centric information under the EHDS.

UNCAN-CONNECT is building on existing European Research Infrastructure (BBMRI, EOSC4CANCER, CanSERV, EUCAIM) to enable seamless storage, access, sharing, and processing of data cancer in a decentralized Collaborative Network of EU member states

Interoperability:

The ability of different health information systems, software, and devices to exchange, interpret, and use data seamlessly across organizational or national boundaries.

Real-world data (RWD)

Health data collected as part of clinical care including electronic health records, insurance claims data, or patient registries.

RWE (Real-World Evidence):

Clinical or health-related insights derived from analysing real-world data (RWD).

Federated Data Analysis :

A method of analysing data that is distributed across multiple sources or locations, without moving the data to a central repository, and only algorithms or aggregated results are shared.

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CANDLE is a EU Horizon funded Coordination and Support Action (2025-2028) of 40 partners, 20 countries providing tools and support for Member States to set up National Cancer Data Nodes.

**National Cancer data
Node DeveLopErs**

European Health Data Space

National Cancer Data Nodes (NCDN)

- First disease-specific implementation of the EHDS
- Federated hubs, standardising and harmonising cancer data within their country/region.
- Building block of UNCAN.eu (UNCAN-Connect)
- Supports the European Cancer Patient Digital Centre (EU-CIP)

First Disease Specific Implementation

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Supporting NCDN Establishment

- Establish national cancer data nodes for cancer data holders
- Improve data quality of cancer data at source
- All cancer datasets have a metadata record in the EU EHDS/NCDN catalogue
- Develop common dataset variables for cancer datasets
- Provide tools for cancer data analysis to be used in secure processing environments (SPEs)